

Lung Single-Cell Transcriptomics in Alpha-1 Antitrypsin Deficiency

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Supplemental Methods

To study the single-cell transcriptomic signature of AATD, lung single-cell RNA-sequencing (scRNA-seq) data from a study of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) were obtained from the Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO: GSE136831) and the Short Read Archive (SRA: SRP395406). Whole lung tissue samples were profiled by Sauler and colleagues (1) using the 10x Genomics Chromium Single Cell 3' v2 platform. Phenotype data for each subject includes age, sex, race and ever-smoker and COPD status (2). The focus was on data from the 17 former smokers diagnosed with COPD.

SERPINA1 genotype

The single-cell RNA-sequencing read files from the Short Read Archive (SRP395406) were used to identify the *SERPINA1* genotype for each of the 17 COPD subjects. The Genome Analysis Toolkit (GATK) (3) RNA-seq variant discovery pipeline from the Broad Institute (gatk4-rnaseq-germline-snps-indels version 1.1.1) was used to detect single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP) variants within the second reads of the scRNA-seq data. The fastq read files were converted to unmapped bam files (uBAM) using the FastqToSam command (4) and merged with additional files when necessary to create one uBAM file for each subject using the MergeSamFiles command (4). With GENCODE (5) Release 19 reference files, the variant at genomic location 94,844,947 of Chromosome 14 (rs28929474) within the output variant call format (VCF) files contained the *SERPINA1* Z allele calls. The S (rs17580), I (rs28931570) and F (rs28929470) alleles were also examined in the VCF files to determine the *SERPINA1* genotype of each subject (6).

Single-cell gene expression

The R package Seurat (7) was used to create data objects for quality control and analysis with the scRNA-seq counts matrix and cell metadata from GEO. Sauler and colleagues (1, 2) mapped the sequencing reads to GRCh38 Release 91, creating an expression set for 45,947 genes across 69,456 cells for the 17 COPD subjects. To observe cell-type clustering and data quality, Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection (UMAP) plots were created using the Seurat functions SCTransform, RunPCA, RunUMAP, DimPlot and FeaturePlot (UMAP plot with gene expression highlighting). Cell sub-types with quality, cell cycle or gene symbol related annotations (i.e.

CellCycle, LowInfo, SubjSpec, MT-tRNAs and FOYN4+) were excluded from the analyses. The cells labeled by Sauler et al. (1) as T cells (alongside T_Regulatory and T_Cytotoxic cell classifications) were reclassified by first excluding T cells not classified as either CD4 or CD8 T cells by the Human Lung Cell Atlas (HLCA) (8), then classifying the remaining T cells as either T_Regulatory or T_Cytotoxic using the HLCA data. Cell types with zero cell counts for any of the MZ and ZZ subjects were excluded from the analysis. Cells classified as multiplets were excluded, as were cells with greater than 20% mitochondrial expression content or less than 1,000 transcripts. Data for genes with zero expression counts across all cells were removed from the cleaned data.

A pseudobulk dataset was created from the cleaned scRNA-seq data using the AggregateExpression function in Seurat (7). This procedure collapsed the single-cell gene expression data into gene-by-subject matrices for each cell type by summing the gene counts across the cells for each subject for each of the cell types. The pseudobulk expression data for each cell type were TMM normalized using the calcNormFactors and cpm functions in the R package edgeR (9) to identify genes with outlying expression levels and to examine the mean expression levels of *SERPINA1* in each cell type.

Differential gene expression and pathway analyses

Associations between gene expression and *SERPINA1* Z allele dosage (MM=0, MZ=1 and ZZ=2) were tested in each cell type using the R package DESeq2 (10) with the cell-type specific pseudobulk data, a conservative approach to identifying statistically significant differential expression in scRNA-seq data (11). The statistical model included the covariates age and sex (model: expression ~ Z.dosage + age + sex). For each cell type, the genes with zero counts across all subjects were excluded. Using the TMM normalized expression data within each of the *SERPINA1* genotype groups, genes with expression in any subject greater than two standard deviations from the mean in any genotype group were excluded from the differential gene expression (DGE) analysis. Output from DESeq2 includes p-values adjusted for multiple testing (10). Intersections of DGE results across cell types were examined using an UpSet plot via the R package UpSetR (12).

Pathway analysis was performed for each of the cell types using Gene Set Enrichment Analysis (GSEA) via the R package gage (13, 14). Prior to GSEA the genes were sorted by expression direction of effect, using both the association p-values and the regression beta from the Z dosage DGE analysis (ordering by: $-\log_{10}(p\text{-value}) * \text{sign}(\log_2(\beta))$) (14). The Hallmark gene sets from MSigDB (15) were used to test enrichment of canonical pathways in the DGE findings. GSEA in smaller studies lacking statistical power leverages DGE results that may not be statistically significant (14). In cell types lacking statistically significant DGE results, caution is urged when interpreting the impact of those pathways.

Pathway enrichment results were summarized in a heatmap using the GSEA q-values with the labeledHeatmap function in the R package WGCNA (16). Networks were created using the R package igraph (17) with the GEM force-directed layout algorithm, where the network edges (connections) represent a significant enrichment of the particular pathway in the DGE results for the connected cell type and highlight cell-cell relationships based on shared pathway activity.

Supplemental Figures

Figure E1. *SERPINA1* mean expression in each cell type, created using the TMM normalized pseudobulk expression data

Figure E2. UMAP plot of scRNA-seq data with (A) cell types labeled and (B) shading to highlight level of *SERPINA1* expression

Column #	Genes at intersection
6	<i>IL6, RNU2-63P, IER2, ENSG00000254281, TCOF1, DUSP1, KLF2, GABPB1</i>
7	<i>ENSG00000267519</i>
8	<i>ZFP36</i>
9	<i>FOS</i>
10	<i>KLF6, ENSG00000274213</i>

Figure E3. Intersection of statistically significant (FDR<0.05) results from differential gene expression analyses across cell types

Figure E4. Heatmap created using the up-regulated hallmark pathway enrichment analysis results (q-values shown).

Figure E5. Heatmap created using the up-regulated hallmark pathway enrichment analysis results (q-values shown).

Supplemental Tables

Table E1. COPD study subjects in scRNA-seq data from Sauler et al. (1)

Genotype	MM (n=11)	MZ (n=1)	ZZ (n=3)
Age in years (mean +/- sd)	63.3 +/- 4.8	62 +/- NA	62.3 +/- 6.8
Sex (Female / Male)	5 / 6	0 / 1	2 / 1
All subjects were former smokers with COPD, of white race			

Table E2. Quality control process for scRNA-seq data

Cells		Genes	
COPD only (n=18 subjects, 37 cell types)	69,456	Initial COPD dataset	45,947
Excluded never smoker (MM genotype) (n=17)	62,942	Remove genes with zero expression	41,240
Excluded two MS genotype (n=15)	53,610		
Removed multiplets	52,672		
MT and feature count filters	43,686		
Outlying cell types removed *	38,959		
Drop cell types # with zero cells for ZZ or MZ (30 cell types)	38,402		
Drop T cells with discordant HLCA classification @	38,387		
Reclassified 2,578 T cells as T_Regulatory (29 cell types)	38,387		
Reclassified 891 T cells as T_Cytotoxic (29 cell types)	38,387		
Cells included in analysis (n=15, 29 cell types)	38,387		
* CellCycle, LowInfo, SubjSpec, MT-tRNAs and FOXN4+ annotations # Aberrant_Basaloid, Basal, DC_Langerhans, DC_Mature, ILC_A, VE_Arterial, and VE_Peribronchial cells @ Alveolar macrophages, B cells, DC2, NK cells, T cells proliferating			

Table E3. Cell counts across study subjects (gray == MM genotype, blue == MZ and green == ZZ)

Cell type	052CO	056CO	137CO	152CO	153CO	186CO	192CO	193CO	194CO	207CO	217CO	235CO	237CO	238CO	23CO
ATI	91	13	4	30	1	3	29	29	13	8	14	1	30	10	16
ATII	70	58	1	100	8	0	11	23	2	57	26	121	63	46	2
B	68	97	0	11	5	15	156	103	88	360	75	115	427	88	57
B_Plasma	20	93	0	30	3	7	15	1	4	72	3	45	75	18	9
cDC1	18	25	0	32	21	18	43	19	64	13	3	25	44	27	4
cDC2	64	92	0	122	40	24	177	135	3	46	37	51	164	68	29
Ciliated	14	92	0	7	31	40	88	154	4	23	70	70	42	14	7
Club	6	10	0	14	17	0	29	88	6	29	42	54	13	9	2
cMonocyte	230	159	0	59	19	104	126	340	2	56	60	80	294	21	192
Fibroblast	19	12	0	31	30	9	7	5	2	59	4	35	37	23	6
Goblet	5	2	1	4	3	1	18	11	1	4	9	16	0	0	2
ILC_B	3	3	0	3	2	4	17	7	10	5	2	6	7	2	2
Lymphatic	24	24	2	63	55	24	6	24	0	7	14	30	33	7	4
Macrophage	94	371	4	399	322	641	377	244	16	297	68	258	444	335	217
Alveolar	176	1087	1	1971	1858	1589	2480	1406	19	386	192	458	114	535	892
Mast	9	16	0	14	2	4	8	29	2	3	4	21	170	46	5
Mesothelial	5	8	0	28	28	19	22	26	2	37	7	9	35	3	2
Myofibroblast	40	35	3	72	6	4	1	1	0	32	6	56	18	25	14
ncMonocyte	130	150	1	98	9	49	143	716	4	65	81	31	219	59	27
NK	196	174	0	106	36	124	222	877	178	207	260	102	122	24	56
pDC	5	14	0	17	2	2	7	34	24	14	2	12	12	3	2
Pericyte	9	0	0	2	1	1	0	0	0	6	2	10	11	4	2
PNEC	0	0	0	1	2	0	1	0	1	1	2	0	1	0	1
SMC	10	2	1	12	2	0	0	0	0	9	7	4	9	4	4
T_Cytotoxic	984	428	0	41	16	246	1233	635	218	196	252	102	82	137	81
T_Regulatory	469	376	0	61	11	80	559	289	199	188	152	36	93	121	102
VE_Capillary_A	39	4	3	3	1	1	0	1	0	13	5	0	18	1	5
VE_Capillary_B	65	15	12	13	1	3	0	3	0	14	12	4	21	5	16
VE_Venous	3	1	0	6	5	4	2	2	1	4	4	3	4	0	6

ATI == alveolar epithelial type I cells, AT2 == alveolar epithelial type II cells, cDC == conventional dendritic cells, cMonocyte == classical monocytes, ILC == innate lymphoid cells, ncMonocyte == non-classical monocyte, NK == natural killer cells, pDC == plasmacytoid dendritic cells, PNEC == pulmonary neuroendocrine cells, SMC == smooth muscle cells, T_Cytotoxic == CD8 T cells, T_Regulatory == CD4 T cells, VE_Capillary_A == vascular endothelial - aerocyte capillary, VE_Capillary_B == vascular endothelial - general capillary, VE_Venous == vascular endothelial venous cells (from Sauler et al. (1))

- 28,874 cells from MM genotype subjects
- 2,537 cells from MZ genotype subjects
- 6,975 cells from ZZ genotype subjects

Table E4. Differential gene expression summary from analysis of associations with *SERPINA1* Z allele dosage

Cell type	Total genes	Results with p-value < 0.05	Results with adjusted p-value < 0.05
Alveolar Macrophage	9859	920	72
Interstitial Macrophage	3995	303	26
ATII	12187	169	0
ncMonocyte	11117	248	5
cMonocyte	4120	241	12
ATI	8595	118	0
cDC2	14693	361	0
Goblet	8880	183	1
Club	12803	261	0
Ciliated	15767	537	0
Mast	6430	89	0
cDC1	10791	228	1
NK	14472	541	1
pDC	7708	111	0
VE Venous	6710	39	0
B	14324	414	2
Myofibroblast	10370	133	1
B_Plasma	10686	108	0
VE Capillary B	7775	88	0
SMC	9546	47	0
Fibroblast	10457	128	0
VE_Capillary_A	6447	34	0
T_Regulatory	14483	631	0
ILC B	5521	60	0
T_Cytotoxic	15509	667	0
Lymphatic	10632	153	0
Mesothelial	11341	195	0
PNEC	11399	10	0
Pericyte	9278	31	0

AT1 == alveolar epithelial type I cells, AT2 == alveolar epithelial type II cells, cDC == conventional dendritic cells, cMonocyte == classical monocytes, ILC == innate lymphoid cells, ncMonocyte == non-classical monocyte, NK == natural killer cells, pDC == plasmacytoid dendritic cells, PNEC == pulmonary neuroendocrine cells, SMC == smooth muscle cells, T_Cytotoxic == CD8 T cells, T_Regulatory == CD4 T cells, VE_Capillary_A == vascular endothelial - aeryocyte capillary, VE_Capillary_B == vascular endothelial - general capillary, VE_Venous == vascular endothelial venous cells

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